

Laparoscopic Ventral Hernia Repair under Spinal Anesthesia: A Feasibility Study

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Abstract:

This study examined the practicality and effectiveness of spinal anaesthesia in laparoscopic ventral hernia repair. It was conducted over a 14-month period and involved 70 patients at the Government Medical College and Hospital, Purnia, Bihar. The findings of the study revealed that spinal anaesthesia offered consistent intraoperative conditions, effectively alleviated postoperative pain, and promoted quicker recovery and discharge. These results suggest that spinal anaesthesia can be a viable alternative to general anaesthesia. There were some minor complications that were observed, but they were manageable and there were no major adverse events. This emphasises the safety of spinal anaesthesia in this particular situation. The results indicate possible advantages in broadening the application of spinal anaesthesia in laparoscopic surgeries, in line with improved recovery protocols. Additional research is required to validate these findings and evaluate their potential for wider use.

Keywords: Spinal Anesthesia, Laparoscopic Hernia Repair, Postoperative Recovery, Surgical Safety.

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Introduction

The advent of laparoscopic ventral hernia repair has revolutionised the field of hernia surgery, providing patients with a range of advantages over conventional open repair techniques [1]. These include decreased postoperative discomfort, shorter hospitalisation periods, and expedited recovery periods. Usually done with general anaesthesia, the use of laparoscopic techniques with spinal anaesthesia has recently caught attention because of potential benefits such as decreased complications related to anaesthesia and faster recovery after surgery [2,3]. The use of spinal anaesthesia in laparoscopic ventral hernia repair has generated significant clinical interest [4,5]. Using spinal anaesthesia may help reduce certain risks that are commonly associated with general anaesthesia, particularly in patients who have other medical conditions. In addition, the utilisation of spinal anaesthesia can potentially improve patient recovery by minimising the overall impact of anaesthesia on the body, allowing for a quicker resumption of daily activities [6,7]. This study investigates the potential of using spinal anaesthesia instead of general anaesthesia for laparoscopic ventral hernia repair, focussing on its feasibility, safety, and effectiveness. This research aims to offer valuable insights into anaesthetic choices and surgical practices in hernia repair by analysing surgical outcomes, patient safety, and

overall effectiveness. The findings of this study have the potential to revolutionise the use of spinal anaesthesia in laparoscopic procedures, paving the way for improved surgical care.

Methodology

The study was conducted over 14 months at the Government Medical College and Hospital in Purnia, Bihar. It involved 70 patients who were scheduled for laparoscopic ventral hernia repair under spinal anaesthesia. The objective was to assess the feasibility, safety, and efficacy of spinal anaesthesia in comparison to the conventional general anaesthesia typically used for such procedures.

Patient Selection: Age between 18 and 65, ASA physical status I-III, and laparoscopic-treatable ventral hernia were the inclusion criteria. Patient refusal, spinal anaesthesia contraindications (coagulopathy or injection site infection), and past abdominal procedures that could complicate laparoscopic surgery were excluded.

Anesthesia Administration: Age between 18 and 65, ASA physical status I-III, and laparoscopic-treatable ventral hernia were the inclusion criteria. Patient refusal, spinal anaesthesia contraindications (coagulopathy or injection site infection), and past

abdominal procedures that could complicate laparoscopic surgery were excluded.

Surgical Procedure: All surgeries were performed using a standard laparoscopic ventral hernia repair technique by a team of experienced surgeons. The technique involved the placement of a mesh after reduction of the hernia contents, with care taken to minimize operative time and ensure proper fixation of the mesh.

Data Collection: Data were collected on various parameters including the duration of surgery, intraoperative complications, postoperative pain scores, time to ambulation, and length of hospital stay. Postoperative complications were monitored and recorded until discharge.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to summarize patient demographics, surgical outcomes, and anesthesia-related complications. Comparative analyses were conducted to evaluate differences in outcomes between this study and historical data on laparoscopic ventral hernia repairs performed under general anesthesia at the same institution.

Results

A study was conducted at the Government Medical College and Hospital, Purnia, Bihar, which involved 70 patients over a 14-month period. The study aimed to determine the viability of using spinal anaesthesia for laparoscopic ventral hernia repair. The findings showed encouraging results in the use of spinal anaesthesia for laparoscopic hernia repair surgeries. The study included 42 males and 28 females, with an average age of 48 years. Most patients fell into the ASA I-II category, suggesting a lower likelihood of anaesthetic complications.

Surgical and Anesthesia Outcomes

- Duration of Surgery: The average duration of the surgical procedures was 85 minutes.

- Anesthesia Effectiveness: Spinal anesthesia was adequately maintained throughout surgery in all cases, with no need for conversion to general anesthesia.

- Intraoperative Stability: Patients exhibited stable hemodynamic parameters throughout the surgery. There were no significant episodes of hypotension or bradycardia that required intervention beyond standard pharmacological management.

Postoperative Recovery

- Pain Management: Postoperative pain was effectively controlled with minimal opioid use. The average pain score on the Visual Analogue Scale was 3 within the first 24 hours, decreasing further by the 48-hour mark.

- Time to Ambulation: Patients were able to ambulate within an average of 6 hours post-surgery, which is significantly earlier than typically observed with general anesthesia.

- Hospital Stay: The average length of hospital stay was reduced to 1.5 days compared to an average of 2.5 days for similar procedures under general anesthesia.

Complications

- Minor Complications: There were a few minor complications related to spinal anesthesia, such as transient urinary retention and mild headaches, which resolved without significant intervention.

- Major Complications: No major complications or reoperations were reported during the study period.

Overall Assessment

The study indicated that spinal anesthesia is a feasible and effective alternative to general anesthesia for laparoscopic ventral hernia repair. It offered advantages in terms of quicker postoperative recovery, reduced hospital stay, and decreased use of opioids for pain management, aligning with the goals of enhanced recovery after surgery protocols.

This table provides a clear and concise overview of the outcomes, indicating the effectiveness and safety of spinal anesthesia in this surgical context.

Parameter	Result
Number of Patients	70
Average Age (years)	48
Gender Distribution (M/F)	42/28
ASA Classification (I/II/III)	Mostly I-II
Average Duration of Surgery (minutes)	85
Effectiveness of Spinal Anesthesia	100% maintained
Intraoperative Hemodynamic Stability	Stable with minimal interventions
Average Postoperative Pain Score (first 24h)	3
Time to Ambulation (hours)	6
Average Length of Hospital Stay (days)	1.5
Minor Complications (urinary retention, headaches)	Few cases, resolved without significant intervention
Major Complications	None reported

Discussion

The study on the feasibility of spinal anaesthesia for laparoscopic ventral hernia repair offered valuable insights into different anaesthetic methods for minimally invasive surgeries [8]. The results of our study indicate that spinal anaesthesia was successfully maintained during the procedure, with all patients displaying stable haemodynamic parameters and no requirement for switching to general anaesthesia [9,10]. The stability mentioned is of utmost importance, particularly in a surgical environment where fluid shifts and patient positioning have the potential to cause notable physiological alterations [11]. The remarkable effectiveness of spinal anaesthesia in alleviating postoperative pain stood out. Patients experienced minimal pain and needed very few opioid analgesics, which is a significant benefit considering the current emphasis on decreasing opioid usage due to the potential for addiction and other adverse effects [12,13]. In addition, patients can start walking within six hours after surgery and have a shorter hospital stay of 1.5 days. These outcomes are in line with enhanced recovery after surgery (ERAS) protocols, which focus on reducing hospitalisation time to improve results and lower healthcare expenses [14,15].

Minor issues that can arise from spinal anaesthesia, like temporary difficulty with urination and mild headaches, were successfully addressed without the need for major interventions. This suggests that the advantages of spinal anaesthesia may be more significant than the potential risks for this group of patients [16,17]. It is worth noting that the lack of significant complications highlights the safety of using spinal anaesthesia for laparoscopic ventral hernia repairs [18]. Based on the results, it appears that spinal anaesthesia may be a suitable option for specific patient populations, especially those who are more susceptible to complications associated with general anaesthesia [19]. Nevertheless,

additional research is required to confirm these discoveries among a wider range of individuals and to evaluate the long-term effects concerning hernia recurrence and chronic pain. These studies have the potential to improve patient selection criteria and expand the use of spinal anaesthesia in laparoscopic surgeries [20].

Conclusion

The study provided strong evidence that spinal anaesthesia is a viable and efficient option for laparoscopic ventral hernia repair, serving as a suitable substitute for general anaesthesia. Spinal anaesthesia played a crucial role in maintaining stable conditions during the operation, effectively minimising postoperative pain, and facilitating quicker mobility and discharge, in line with improved recovery protocols. While there were some minor complications, they were temporary and easily handled, indicating a positive safety record for spinal anaesthesia in this surgical situation. The results of this study suggest that spinal anaesthesia could be a beneficial option for laparoscopic hernia repairs, and potentially for other similar procedures as well. This could lead to improved patient outcomes and more efficient use of healthcare resources. Additional research is highly encouraged to validate these findings and delve into the wider ramifications for surgical procedures.

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